

EOSC as an indispensable component of the FP10 European Partnership portfolio

OPINION PAPER by the EOSC Steering Board expert group (E03756)

Overview

In this opinion paper, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Steering Board outlines the case for EOSC as a distinct work-programme based European Partnership under the next framework programme FP10 (Horizon Europe 2028-2034), highlighting its horizontal relevance for a future portfolio of European Partnerships. The EOSC Steering Board formulates recommendations relevant for the selection, the structure and establishment of a European Partnership for EOSC, to empower EOSC as Europe's trusted, secure and sovereign research data ecosystem.

1. Introduction

Over the past decade, research has been reshaped by the fast-growing scale of data, the growing expectations of accelerated discovery, and the arrival of artificial intelligence (AI)-supported methods. Still scientific progress requires connectivity of knowledge and tools: across disciplines, institutions, and borders; across data, tools, and services; and across the infrastructure stack - from storage to high-performance computing.

In this rapidly shifting landscape, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) has undergone a fundamental transformation. The developmental trajectory of EOSC can be defined by three phases of maturity:

- The Foundational Phase (2016–2020): EOSC emerged as a policy ambition, a "cloud for research" intended to break down the silos of European science; this was a period focused on consensus-building and defining the EOSC long-term objectives.
- The Operational Phase (2021–2027): Under FP9 (Horizon Europe), the EOSC Partnership turned vision and policy into a functional reality^{1 2}. The establishment of the EOSC Federation and the launch of the EOSC EU Node and national, e-infrastructure, and thematic EOSC Nodes moved the project from a concept to a distributed yet connected infrastructure, that will deliver specific added value for users, accelerating discovery, collaboration, and reuse.
- The Implementation and Impact Phase (2028-2034 and beyond): In FP10 (Horizon Europe 2028-2034) [2]³, EOSC must transition from a project to a strategic capability. The focus shifts from providing availability of resources to their seamless orchestration in support of research excellence, Europe's digital competitiveness and research security.

Across these phases, EOSC has been progressively maturing towards a durable and resilient European strategic capability in science. This evolution responds to a challenge in European research: how to turn distributed, nationally and community-owned resources into a system that can work seamlessly

¹ During the operational phase, EOSC is steered through an informal EOSC Tripartite Governance, formed by the European Commission (EC), the Member States of the European Union (MS) and Associated Countries (AC) to Horizon Europe represented in the EOSC Steering Board and the EOSC Association representing the research community and being partner of the EC in the current EOSC Partnership.

² The activities of the current EOSC Partnership are continuously monitored and periodically reported. This includes the annual reporting activity of the additional activities plan (AAP) of contributions and their actual provision as well as the biennial reporting activity, see e.g. [1].

³ This document is based on the proposal of FP10 by the European Commission from July 2025 and doesn't preempt the legislative procedure within the Council of the European Union and the European Parliament.

at European scale for researchers. EOSC's added value lies precisely here: by bringing Europe's investments (repositories, infrastructures, services, and community resources) together into a usable, trusted, and interoperable research commons layer, so researchers can find, access, combine, and reuse data, software, workflows, and services more easily. EOSC increases the return on prior public investments, strengthens reuse and reproducibility, and provides the trustworthy data needed for AI-enabled science, while preserving the distributed ownership and autonomy of national and thematic communities and infrastructures.

To ensure sustainable impact, EOSC must move in this third phase from a project-based model to a stable structural framework, that supports the ERA and provides the agility and resilience needed to respond to a shifting global landscape.

To make this transition a reality and strengthen collaboration in FP10, we recommend establishing EOSC as **a distinct work-programme-based European Partnership, anchored in practical cooperation with other strategic initiatives.**

This transition is essential for four reasons:

- **Multiannual sustainability:** A partnership supports stable, multi-year planning for EOSC Federation development and operations, avoiding interruptions between project cycles and reducing fragmentation compared with isolated projects.
- **One shared investment logic:** A partnership translates EOSC strategy into a single, priority-based implementation plan, reducing duplication between EU- and national-level actions and ensuring that activities create synergy and complement each other.
- **Flexibility and agility:** Within that common plan, priorities and budgets can be rebalanced as EOSC matures (e.g. scaling what works, addressing gaps, responding to new policy, technology, or community needs) without redesigning the whole programme.
- **Europe-wide participation and uptake:** Transparent co-funding of the European Commission (EC) and the Member States of the European Union (MS) and Associated Countries to Horizon Europe (AC) enables sustained, multi-layer support for cross-border processes and elements, such as federation coordination, shared trust and interoperability components, and access to cross-border services, so participation does not depend on uneven national capacity and researchers across Europe can reuse resources.

EOSC would act as a shared foundation for research data across Europe, providing common tools, standards, and services that make it easier for researchers to manage and share data. As a horizontal European Partnership, EOSC would support all research activities across FP10, complementing sector-specific initiatives rather than replacing them. It would work closely with key EU initiatives such as the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking, RAISE (Resources for AI Science in Europe), ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures), and the wider network of European research infrastructures, helping to align data, computing, and AI capacities. In addition, EOSC would serve as a connection pathway between the European research and innovation data space and other Common European Data Spaces, enabling interoperability, data reuse, and cross-sector collaboration.

2. Portfolio relevance of EOSC

At a moment when Europe's competitiveness and values, digital sovereignty, strategic autonomy, and data security are under unprecedented pressure, EOSC becomes far more than a research instrument: it becomes a strategic priority for the Union to build a **resilient, productive, trusted, secure and sovereign knowledge economy**. EOSC is not simply aligned with this EU ambition but is indispensable to delivering it. As such, EOSC's design and operational principles are directly in line with the strategic imperatives outlined in the Competitiveness Compass communication [3]. Furthermore, EOSC underpins Europe's competitiveness and innovation agenda as highlighted in the latest communications on the European Strategy on Research and Technology Infrastructures [4], the AI

Continent Action Plan [5], the AI in Science Strategy [6] and the Data Union Strategy [7]. The creation of European Knowledge Commons to operationalize the fifth freedom through frictionless circulation of knowledge is moreover reinforced by the policy recommendations of the Letta report [8]. The Draghi report [9] identifies the availability of world-leading research and technological infrastructure, capable of serving the whole European ecosystem, as an important factor that would enhance research and innovation capacity, and the Heitor report on the next Framework Programme (Horizon Europe 2028-2034) [10] mentions EOSC as key enabler for the digitalization of research infrastructures.

EOSC empowers Europe's research data ecosystem [11] through the following objectives:

- **EOSC to safeguard European data sovereignty:** EOSC ensures long-term-, secure, and trustworthy access to quality-assessed research data in compliance with EU regulations [12].
- **EOSC to foster European leadership in artificial intelligence:** By unlocking large, diverse, machine actionable FAIR datasets, EOSC directly supports AI development and reduces data scarcity. It also ensures interoperability, provenance, and reproducibility, which mitigate “black box” risks and enable responsible AI.
- **EOSC to increase security in research and data management:** EOSC safeguards sensitive resources while enabling scientific innovation and fostering cross-border, cross-disciplinary collaboration.
- **EOSC to establish the EU Single Market for knowledge:** EOSC plays a central role in removing barriers within the European Single Market for knowledge by enabling seamless sharing and reuse of research data across countries, disciplines, and infrastructures.
- **EOSC to enhance Europe's global scientific competitiveness:** By standardising data sharing protocols and ensuring interoperability across disciplines and borders, EOSC facilitates the interdisciplinary collaboration required to address complex global challenges such as climate change, health, ageing society and inequalities.
- **EOSC to boost European data economy:** EOSC enhances Europe's productivity by transforming fragmented assets into interoperable, high-value capabilities, reducing costly duplication of efforts and maximising the return on public investments.
- **EOSC to empower European values:** By providing open access to FAIR datasets, EOSC empowers researchers, educators, and innovators from all regions to engage in cutting-edge scientific work, democratising access to research resources across Europe.

To conclude, as Europe faces complex global challenges and a competitive international landscape, EOSC stands as a transformative asset, a critical tool for harnessing shared knowledge and trusted quality-assessed data [13], driving breakthrough innovations, adding value to EU data policies and ensuring that the continent remains at the forefront of global research and development. Continued investment in and development of EOSC through an EOSC Partnership under FP10 is therefore not merely beneficial; it is essential for securing Europe's future prosperity and global leadership.

3. Recommendations of the EOSC SB: The case for EOSC as a European Partnership under FP10

3.1 A strengthened EOSC Partnership to deliver on the five EOSC Tasks

We propose positioning EOSC under FP10 as a strengthened EOSC Partnership that encompasses both the EOSC Federation and the broader EOSC ecosystem to deliver on the five EOSC Tasks whose definitions have been developed by the EOSC Tripartite Governance over the duration of FP9, and which are briefly described below.

- **Task 1: Deploying and operating the EOSC EU Node**

The EOSC EU Node should provide a stable European entry point and reference implementation that strengthens federation coherence and usability without becoming the single gateway or the sole provider of core federation functions. Under FP10 it should ensure

reliable baseline capabilities within a multi-entry, multi-provider Federation in which national/multinational, e-infrastructure and thematic nodes serve as primary access points for their communities and provide equivalent federation functions.

- **Task 2: EOSC Federation (nodes, federating capabilities, coordination and operations)**

This task focuses on building, operating and managing the Federation as a functioning system of systems: enrolling and supporting nodes, strengthening interconnection, and ensuring the operational (federating) capabilities that make federation tangible for users. It should prioritise a distributed and resilient architecture, where nodes can interoperate, enabling cross-border service uptake and reducing fragmentation while preserving community ownership and autonomy.

- **Task 3: Enabling a web of FAIR data and services for science**

EOSC's value is realised when researchers can seamlessly find, access, combine and reuse datasets, software, workflows and services across domains and borders. This task should drive the scaling of FAIR data and service provision through systematic onboarding and reusable access interfaces, linking repositories and infrastructures into a machine-actionable "web". It should ensure that practical tools are available to researchers and communities to support co-creation, curation, and reuse of these resources, so that core principles such as quality, and traceability can be embedded by design.

- **Task 4: Research and prototyping new capacities for the EOSC Federation**

Under this Task support will be provided for targeted prototyping that strengthens federation capabilities over time, especially where new methods (including AI) require upgraded approaches to data governance, automation, and reproducibility.

- **Task 5: Enabling Open Science policies and uptake of Open Science practices through EOSC**

A sustainable Federation depends on widespread adoption with researchers acting both as producers of FAIR outputs and active end-users of federated resources. This task should align policy, incentives and capability-building so that transparent sharing and effective reuse of resources become routine across Europe, supported by training, community engagement, and practical guidance and tools.

In this context, the EOSC Federation is the partnership's main operational mechanism that makes EOSC a federated virtual environment for research, and the broader EOSC ecosystem (Open Science initiatives, research communities, and service and data providers, skills and training) constitutes EOSC's user and contributor community.

The Federation's build-up began in 2024 with the EOSC EU Node and the first wave of node enrolment⁴ and now is expanding via consecutive waves. The Federation demonstrates how distributed resources can be connected to deliver added value to users: facilitated discovery and access, and more efficient cross-border reuse of data, tools, and services⁵. The Federation's multi-node structure (national, multinational, thematic, and e-infrastructure nodes) reflects EOSC's ambition to integrate technology with human expertise and social networks.

In the Implementation and Impact Phase (as outlined in the Introduction), EOSC will evolve into a production-grade capability offering a set of interoperable entry points tailored to the needs and expectations of different communities, together with a coherent working environment across the Federation. Through the entry point most relevant to their community, researchers will be able to discover and combine resources from across Europe, run and reuse workflows using connected

⁴ The EOSC Federation build-up process began at the [kick-off meeting in Brussels](#), in March 2025.

⁵ For example three multi node-to-node use cases were presented at the [EOSC Symposium 2025](#): The MCVAl, Galaxy, and REANA.

compute and storage, and publish and share bundled outputs such as data, software, workflows and metadata. Access to these resources will be enabled through federated Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI), allowing users to sign in once and obtain the appropriate level of access under clear and trusted conditions, including where secure environments for sensitive data are required. EOSC will also provide user support and guidance, including through helpdesks.

Because pooling and integrating these resources has specific technical and organisational implications (e.g. interoperability, security and trust, policy alignment, sustainable operations), the partnership under FP10 should structure the EOSC implementation around the five tasks that together ensure a functional Federation and support uptake of resources.

3.2 An EOSC Partnership as key horizontal component

The EOSC Partnership should be a key horizontal component in the FP10 portfolio of partnerships (as outlined in Section 2) and beyond. With its horizontal nature and broad scope, an EOSC Partnership supports all research activities across FP10 with a coherent and harmonised framework for data sharing and data management and related services, as such complementing other sectorial partnerships. Many Horizon Europe thematic communities are already aligning their approaches to EOSC, and several are frontrunners in building nodes of the EOSC Federation. Collaboration with other FP10 partnerships and relevant initiatives could be pursued through appropriate coordination mechanisms to align investments and foster synergies aimed at ensuring that research data within these partnerships and initiatives is consistent with FAIR principles, supported by interoperable approaches to research data management, and reuse, while enabling cross-domain scientific use cases.

At the same time, EOSC should deepen collaboration with broader research communities, and with the future EU research and technology infrastructures governance. This includes ESFRI (European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures) and other bodies to come for e.g. Technology Infrastructures, Digital and/or e-Infra Infrastructures, so that disciplinary excellence and federation at scale reinforce each other. Common advisory bodies, such as the ESFRI-EOSC Task Force, the e-infrastructure reflection group (e-IRG) and the European e-Infrastructures Assembly, have been proven to be efficient tools in this context. EOSC (as the Common European Data Space for Research and Innovation) should also act as a horizontal research and innovation layer that connects to other Common European Data Spaces, by providing trusted access and enabling reuse of research outputs across domains, while respecting sector-specific rules and governance.

3.3 An EOSC Partnership as a key enabler of AI for and in science in Europe

In addition to being a key horizontal component in the overall portfolio as outlined in section 3.2, a distinct partnership will place EOSC also within a strong collaborative ecosystem alongside the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking (including AI Factories and Gigafactories) and RAISE (Resources for AI Science in Europe), linking data, services, and compute. In the context of this emerging AI ecosystem, EOSC will help ensure that individual researchers and research communities (both as data and service producers and users) remain at the centre. EOSC will provide access to AI-enhanced data and tools based on approaches that strengthen transparency and trust, ensuring AI is used in ways that align with research needs and support scientific judgement. Such strong ties expected with EuroHPC and RAISE form a complementary triangle of core building blocks for AI-readiness in science: AI-enhanced research data and services (EOSC), high-performance and quantum computing (EuroHPC), and AI-focused capabilities and uptake (RAISE). Together, these three create the enabling backbone for AI-oriented and AI-supported research across Europe.

We propose strengthened coordination and collaboration between EOSC, EuroHPC, and RAISE, supported by specific mechanisms to ensure that Europe's digital investments are leveraged to their full potential. These mechanisms are a strategic imperative to reinforce Europe's sovereignty, ensuring

that data, compute, and AI ecosystems operate as a coherent European capability, while strictly preserving EOSC's distinct governance and budgetary autonomy.

The collaboration of EOSC with EuroHPC and RAISE should be organised around several working arrangements focused on joint planning, interoperable operations, and flagship use cases, for example:

- Establishing a strategic coordination group: A light governance forum (with clear mandates and no budget pooling) to align roadmaps, identify dependencies, and agree on priorities for cross-initiative actions.
- Joint roadmap: A synchronized planning process to match EOSC data/service evolution with EuroHPC infrastructure upgrades and RAISE capability-building and uptake measures.
- Interoperability-by-design framework: A shared set of technical and policy interfaces to ensure EOSC resources can be accessed and processed on EuroHPC infrastructure and used within RAISE-supported AI research with AI outputs bundled for potential inclusion within EOSC.

The joint roadmap and interoperability-by-design framework should consider the concept of Data Labs according to the AI in Science Strategy [6] and the Data Union Strategy [7]. In that regard, a structured operational agreement should enable the trusted flow of data between EOSC, linking Data Labs and EuroHPC infrastructure with clear access conditions and, where appropriate, feed resulting datasets, metadata, metadata schema, workflows, and documentation back into EOSC for discovery, reuse, and reproducibility. This should be supported by aligned interfaces, standards, and governance approaches. In this way, EOSC would provide the trusted research data commons and an enabling layer for AI-enhanced data and services for science, while Data Labs would complement this through additional data preparation and transformation functions.

3.4 An EOSC Partnership Governance with a focus on Tripartite

Key principles under FP10

EOSC should remain governed through a shared model that secures strategic direction, inclusivity and long-term sustainability (including beyond FP10), while ensuring meaningful participation of the research communities so that EOSC remains user driven. Governance should be separate from day-to-day operations, and the decision-making structure should reflect partners' public responsibilities and financial commitments (EC and MS/AC). The EOSC Association and the EOSC Federation should provide structured mechanisms to consolidate user needs and implementation evidence, anchored in the EOSC Tasks described above under Section 3.1.

Tripartite steering and decision-making

EOSC should continue to follow a Tripartite approach bringing together the European Commission, the MS/AC, and the EOSC Association. Following the rules for partnerships under FP10, these three parties can either be partners or, if that will not be possible, the EOSC Association will take a strong advisory role in the future governance, ensuring that all three continue to contribute to the steering of EOSC. Details should be laid out in the MoU of the partnership.

Federation coordination, conflict-of-interest safeguards, and technology neutrality

To make the EOSC Federation work in practice, its governance under FP10 should include a function (e.g. "Federation Management") to coordinate the day-to-day operation and evolution of the Federation across nodes and contributors, keep implementation coherent, and report transparently on progress and performance. This function should be entrusted to the EOSC Association acting as a neutral, public-interest-driven coordinator subject to transparency, accountability, and conflict-of-interest safeguards. For this purpose, the EOSC Association needs to evolve under FP10, as well as for a broad representation of EOSC users.

Support for agility and inclusivity

To strengthen agility without creating parallel decision-making, the Tripartite setting may be supported by lightweight thematic advisory bodies (e.g. from expert panels) and structured community input coordinated by the EOSC Association. Inclusivity can be supported through flexible, tiered participation modalities for MS/AC, recognising different levels of readiness and enabling countries to contribute (cash and in-kind) in transparent ways that can evolve over time. These modalities will allow countries to smoothly move between tiers along readiness pathways as their capacities and needs change.

3.5 An EOSC Partnership based on partners' commitments

Under FP10, continuing EOSC as a partnership requires a strong commitment by the partners, e.g. by the EC and the MS/AC. A significant contribution on the MS/AC side should be envisioned. To reach this goal, the aim is to engage all Member States and a significant fraction of the Associated Countries in the partnership.

Contributions by partners other than the Union should include financial commitment, as well as tangible in-kind contributions that directly benefit the build-up and operations of the EOSC Federation.

Work programmes under the partnership should include co-financed actions, in which beneficiaries contribute in-kind to obtain funding from the partnership. This will ensure a significant contribution by the users and providers of the EOSC and leverage their engagement.

The partnership will rely on regular monitoring of the contributions by the partners, based on KPIs and providing measures for the impact of the activities of EOSC.

3.6 An EOSC Partnership with Juste Retour and Widening to build Europe-wide legitimacy and capacity

The EOSC Partnership should ideally be set up including all MS/AC, and with contributions from each country that reflect their economic standing and the benefit their communities receive from the EOSC.

However, in order to avoid an unbalanced situation in which an EU wide EOSC Federation and work programme is financed by a few, a juste-retour approach should be considered. The basis for the juste-retour calculation should be contributions of a clear financial value to the partnership.

This approach also helps prevent EOSC from drifting into a “two-speed” Europe, where only a few countries produce and shape the ecosystem. Europe-wide legitimacy requires that all European regions can participate in a meaningful way.

In this context, a juste-retour principle should be considered as a baseline capacity needed to be federation-ready. This is also a fairness mechanism that can make participation credible across different starting positions, while strengthening the Federation’s diversity and coverage.

Widening in EOSC should be treated as a practical instrument to build real EOSC-readiness and capability (within EOSC Federation and broader EOSC ecosystem), not solely as a soft generic “participation” label. The objective is that researchers across Europe are both producers of FAIR outputs and effective users of federated resources, so that EOSC can support their day-to-day research practice. The offer and consumption of cost-intensive services in the EOSC Federation also deserves to be recognised both for juste-retour and capacity- and readiness-building mechanisms, including widening instruments where appropriate.

Juste-retour and Widening must be complementary. They should be designed together and applied carefully to avoid overlap or double funding, for instance:

- Widening helps communities become ready and capable, while
- Juste-retour ensures fair, measurable, and operational participation in the Federation through concrete contributions.

4. Conclusion

FP10 will transform EOSC from an accumulating set of components into a coherently governed European capability with a stable mandate through predictable delivery cycles, a clear accountability framework, and a credible pathway from federation-building to routine use. It becomes the place where national and European investments align around shared operational priorities, not just shared principles, enabling EOSC to function as infrastructure, “system of systems”.

The partnership ensures continuity and delivery, protecting past investments while creating the conditions for impact at scale. A distinct EOSC Partnership under FP10 is therefore not an expansion of scope, but the structural consolidation of what Europe has already built, and the foundation required to make Europe’s AI, data and infrastructure investments scientifically usable and trusted across borders and disciplines.

EOSC should therefore be positioned in FP10 as Europe’s trusted data commons: sovereign, resilient, and designed for day-to-day use. With the Tripartite Governance and a blended and trackable funding model, EOSC can deliver a high-class European capability that boosts research discovery, reproducibility, and innovation, strengthens digital sovereignty, enables responsible AI leadership, and maximises the impact of Europe’s R&I investments.

To provide an impactful EOSC, we recommend the following:

1. Establish EOSC as a distinct work-programme based European Partnership under FP10.
2. Continue to develop EOSC along the five tasks established during FP9.
3. Keep the EOSC Federation at the focus of the EOSC development.
4. Build a European AI-enhanced ecosystem for science by collaborating and aligning EOSC with EuroHPC, RAISE and other Common European Data Spaces.
5. Continue EOSC under a Tripartite Governance involving the European Commission, Member States (MS) and Associated Countries (AC), and the EOSC Association as a representative of the user communities. In a situation where the EOSC Association cannot be partner in the partnership, the EOSC Association should take a strong advisory role in the future governance, ensuring that all three continue to contribute to the steering of EOSC.
6. Entrust the EOSC Association with the coordination of the EOSC Federation.
7. Aim for a partnership that includes all MS and a significant share of the AC of FP10.
8. Foresee a significant contribution from the MS/AC side, while recognising tangible in-kind contributions to the EOSC Federation as a form of partner’s participation.
9. Set up the partnership in such a way that partner countries see an investment and financing of activities in their countries at a level at least as high as their contributions with a financial value to the partnership.
10. Accompany the partnership, and the continued build-up and operations of the EOSC Federation and its nodes, with widening mechanisms.

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In this opinion paper the EOSC Steering Board elaborated further on how Europe can ensure that its scientific data and data-services – and the knowledge they represent – remain permanently accessible, verifiable, and secure, by reinforcing the EOSC Federation, aligning national and EU initiatives, and embedding legal and operational clarity. Thereby, European sovereignty in research data is all but isolation. It requires the ability to maintain open, fair, and trustworthy scientific collaboration, grounded in resilience, interoperability, and shared values.
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In this opinion paper, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Steering Board reflects on how EOSC can build a more secure and scientifically credible environment for open research by integrating automated validation systems, certification mechanisms, legal protections, and a culture of continuous monitoring. The recommendations form a roadmap toward a federated infrastructure where FAIR data is not only findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable—but also trusted, protected, and resilient in the face of future challenges. Data quality and security are therefore at the core of the strategy for open science and open innovation.
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In this opinion paper on the future Framework Programme 10 the EOSC Steering Board defines EOSC as a cornerstone of the EU’s research and digital policies, a European strategic asset for a more productive and efficient research and innovation ecosystem, driving innovation, economic growth, and competitiveness. In the paper, the EOSC Steering Board recommends that FP10 provides dedicated support for the development and operation of the EOSC Federation as a European Knowledge Commons, which will provide access to publicly funded research, data sets, and other research outputs.